

“Feeding my Search”

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Abstract

Existing “Search Engines” span the content of websites: they help you find a web-page which relates to the information you seek. However, we have started using web content for many other purposes: for language research, media monitoring, selling products, promotion of brands, as alternative for a TV. This has resulted in many overlapping ad-hoc solutions to improve information discovery.

By carefully reorganizing the way we collect and process information, constructing a traditional “Search Engine” becomes a composition of activities which can be shared with other information discovery applications. It enables cooperation and gradual evolution. This design works with *feeds* which are far more evolved than for instance XMPP or RSS-feeds.

1 Growing pains

The early search engines, like AltaVista, had a relatively easy task. Although internet connections were slow, the website content was simple: text with a few supporting images. The HTML was simple without JavaScript loading page fragments, content modifying by CSS, relation polluting link-farms, and domain pirates. No take-down notices, no fake-news and political radicals: just simple vending machines and access to academic information.

Over time, the virtual internet behavior became the same battle-ground as our real society, or –because its international and open character– even much worse. “Search Engines” have been patched to defend themselves better. They extended their power, but have clearly lost grip on the situation. They sometimes pretend to be fair, but practically keep the user restricted into business conglomerates. Not only for the commercial reason, but also as protection against abuse.

For example, when you search Google for “harddisk”, it reports ‘About 196,000,000

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results' as textual hit score. Then, it shows Google-shop harddisks for sale. Followed by a few (Google revenue) advertisements. Usually (also in this case) followed by a useful Wikipedia page. Followed by seven shops which use SEO-farms to get high visibility. You get some images of harddisks. For many search queries you'll see a bunch of (Google-owned) YouTube videos.

Actually, in recent years two useful components were added to the result page: 'Searches related to harddisk' and 'People also ask'. The keyword "harddisk" is far too generic to understand what the visitor is really looking for. Most people will be able to restrict their 196 million initial result back to a meager few million, with this help.

The problems seems insolvable: there are simply not enough words in a language to give all websites a fair chance to be found on the first pages of Google results. Improvements with other than textual help however, are seriously hindered by the economic power of the few business syndicates.

There are new chances to restart the way we maintain information:

- people do not trust the fairness of large (American) companies anymore. they are open to alternatives;
- existing search gets deeper into problems with limitations put by the GDPR. They have not been built to support it;
- copyrights, fake-news, and politics put more and more pressure on big-tech, but they can only patch their systems by hiring people to do boring tasks;
- many companies are unable to get a fair chance, so would welcome a place where they get a better chance to compete;
- most people are now aware of successes of open cooperation models, like Open Source and Wikipedia. They desire an open alternative which respects their rights and privacy.

How to exploit these advantages? Actually, there is a way which is feasible: model internet information exchange to mimic how we have traditionally organized our society and economy. Create a marketplace which enables cooperation, competition, specialization, payments, and voluntary contributions. Connections which respect rules for contracts, copyrights, correction, and privacy.

2 Marketplace

The proposal is to design an information exchange protocol which looks like a Marketplace, on top of existing transport protocols like plain HTTP or XMPP. The standardized messaging components behave like feeds: a party which needs information contacts the party who provides the information as a service in point-to-point stateless communication.

Before getting into composing a search engine as example, let us first describe the main tasks of the infra-structure.

Many of the components needed for the suggested infra-structure do already exist. They mainly lack ways to integrate, and sometimes have economic motives to defend their niche. We must accept that most people need to earn money for their living, but at the same time assure that no-one can claim a special position in the marketplace. This can be achieved by an Open design of the required interfaces. It requires a strong neutral leader, like the EU.

2.1 Authorization

The representation of people and organizations is standardized in the network. Some service components may not need to know who uses them. Other may accept a user-generated cookie. Sensitive components may require a formal prove of a person's identity. The IRMA¹ project shows how to make this work.

People have a personal identity, but also various roles with respect to work, organizations and activities. Some roles add restrictions, some offer additional possibilities: especially when you think about business relations and contacts with the government or banks.

Authorization may contain a *contract*, represented by a certificate. This will often be required, because a lot of the data may accidentally contain facts which are restricted under the GDPR. This needs to be covered explicitly.

2.2 Search

Components provide services, which may be data. The client connects to the component with a request. The component responds. This does not only contain the answer, but also copyright, license, jurisdiction, and expiration date of the content.

The component will demand a maximum revisit speed. It also states a minimum revisit time: clients are required to check-in regularly whether data has been updated or revoked.

What here is referred to as "Search" is actually the exchange of information. Rules of our real-world society (like copyrights and retention) are standardized and enforced via the *contract*. The payload of this search request and response is not centrally standardized.

2.3 Payments

All components of the initial implementation will see a free implementation, to have the lowest threshold to attract new participants. However, in the current reality, even small tasks may be quite complex implement perfectly. Better implementations may not come for free.

¹Radboud University of Nijmegen NL, <https://irma.app>.

For instance “language detection”. There are many open source and commercial programs which discover the language of a text. Some party could provide a simple and free to use component, which does a simple character-count based detection. But that’s not sufficient for everyone: there may be a demand for distinction of dialects. There may be a demand for detection per paragraph, and so on. You may need to pay for these extras: quality comes at a price.

These payments themselves need components which bundle them and connect them to the real world bank transactions.

2.4 Feeds

It is important to realize that some components will handle massive amounts of data with quite some related meta-data. This makes them less suitable for real-time pass-through filtering. When a person searches for a keyword, it is too late to build the index: the component needs to be prepared to answer fast. The components which lead to the search index are not timely bound: minutes or hours processing delay may be acceptable. Such connections are easier to maintain and far more hardware efficient.

Components have to be carefully designed: does it need to store information for a longer time? How fast must it be in its responses? Competitive components will offer different features. But in general, they all work as feeds: you ask, I deliver. Components are regularly polling resources via *feeds*.

3 Construction a Search Engine

In the context of this conference, it is useful to show how this generic component network can implement a traditional website search engine. Simplified, the search engine steps are:

The website has a few ways to help being indexed: `description` and `keywords` fields per page, `sitemaps`, and `robots.txt`.

The crawler is a cluster of servers which scan web-pages, according to a plan. A manual list of media websites makes them be scanned more often. Changes on other pages will be discovered slowly.

The indexer takes the text content of pages, and makes them searchable. More important are discovered links, de-duplication, physical location, and the language used.

The collector translates a user search into a result page. It uses a text-search for words (sloppy), add synonym and typo-smartness, and commercially profitable answers. Page ranking is applied based on many factors, among them are secondary facts recorded by the indexer and the history of the requestor.

The browser not only displays the result, but also helps to extend the knowledge about the requestor.

How would this look like in a feed-oriented structure?

The simplest solution is to start delivering a feed: to offer access to the collector or index. This would enable DuckDuckGo to get a better quality of results, where it now has to simulate a browser to collect results.

A second stage of development would be to split the collector in a component which ranks the answers from the text search, and a separate component which adds advertisements and follows user behavior. This is not an unusual structure: when you shop for a hotel room, there are hundreds of affiliate websites which all see the same database but present other selections and with other interfaces.

In a third stage, the text index is detached from the additional ranking information. The collected facts about web-page relations (hyperlink network), user behavior, physical location described in the content in relation to the user's location, language and synonyms are split over many different specialized components. Google distributes your simple query over thousands of systems, which all take a fragment of the ranking logic. You want to be able to 'play' with these components, you want to be able to evolve them separately in competition.

Crawling websites is a restraining activity. The only thing the search index wants from the crawling process is to get the latest version of all pages on all websites. To collect those pages is quite expensive and time consuming, but the indexer does not need to be involved: it can do with a rather thin interface and will only benefit from treating it as separate components.

Basically, Crawlers create feeds: data streams. They pump web-pages with static URLs into a feed of pages. First, all pages are scanned. Then they get split into text, links and images. Those get de-duplicated and filtered. Detected changes are offered to the index. Changed pages get revisited sooner than unchanged pages.

4 Helping Crawlers

Let us go one step deeper in a corner of the global plan: discuss new ideas in website crawling.

Websites get plagued with dozens of crawlers. Many sites attempt to keep them away by only allowing Google via the `robots.txt` file. Therefore, scanners ignore that voluntary self-restriction. The constructible approach would be to have an *open* crawler where anyone interested can get the latest data from. ISPs and website owners can help that crawler to improve results.

Four parties which can help improving the indexing the website: the website owner, the ISP hosting the website, and the visitors, and the crawler.

4.1 Help by website owners

The website owner (or the tool used to maintain the website) could feed the changes itself. Or at least answer the questions which pages have changed (not like the sitemap which only lists which pages exist). The owner should give (or restrict) permission for long-time use of GDPR sensitive data. Also, the copyright and license situation should be clear.

4.2 Help by ISPs

Internet providers host zillions of websites, which are all continuously plagued by crawlers. This cost network and hardware resources: when they run a crawler on their own premises, the quality goes up and the operating cost will go down.

4.3 Help by visitors

At the moment, people cannot help information collectors to improve their collection. In the “search engine” sense:

- websites do not have help for search engines, like `description` and `keywords` in each pages. Or no sitemap for their dynamic site;
- websites may on purpose try to fool search engines to get a higher ranking;
- websites may try to lure visitors with incorrectly represent itself;
- websites may contain undesired content, like fake-news or personal pictures;
- websites may attempt fishing or show other criminal behavior.

At the moment, there is no way for website visitors to help other visitors or search engines to improve access to that information.

Web-browsers could get a side-bar, where the user can see what other parties (like Amnesty International and Police). People can also contact other parties with reports about the site via such interface, for instance report criminal behavior to the police.

4.4 Help by the crawler

A crawler infrastructure could be of good help for itself by hinting website owners how to improve their site. For instance, it could feedback on performance, accessibility, broken links, and validity of https certificates. Maybe even flag spelling errors, warn when it detects copyrighted material, and offer lists of reverse links.

5 Summary

The large variation in search related plans for using available information on internet can be supported by a single new concept: a concept which offers a marketplace to many open source, research, and commercial activities. The main benefits are specialization and competition: against the current trend of market domination by a small number of big-tech companies.

The implementation of a “Search Engine” in the proposed component-based structure can help share efforts between the large diversity of applications developed by Open Search Foundation members.

About the Author

Mark Overmeer got his Master in Computing Science from the Radboud University in Nijmegen, The Netherlands in 1990. The title of his thesis was “Real-time fault-tolerance in Multi-Controller systems”, which shows his early love for very complex networks.

After University, he worked as system programmer in the super-computer environment of the NLR, the Royal Netherland Aerospace Centre. He implemented distributed user accounting and backup networks at the time no commercial products were available yet.

After six years at NLR, he worked as UNIX trainer –programming and system administration for professionals– until his side-projects grew too large to be combined with a full-time contract job.

Since 2002, Mark worked as self-employed programmer for many different smaller and larger companies. In the past years (among other projects) full-time for the NCSC: the National Cyber Security Center of the Dutch Ministry of Justice, as developer/maintainer of the website monitoring system Taranis.

His side-track activities have resulted in many different products. For example: a huge satellite image archive (two clusters with each six servers packed with disks), over 70 libraries for the Perl programming language (mainly XML and email related), and over 100 presentations at (mainly Open Source) conferences.

The development of the 10th website in the Netherlands in 1994 triggered his interest for search engines. This led to two papers about that subject contributed for a TERENA-NORDUnet Networking Conference in 1999. The papers were published in IEEE Computer Networking.²³ Mark has made a few attempts to interest people to seriously improve Search Engines since, and recently gave that more focus.

Mark is closely involved with the NLUUG (Dutch Unix User Group), the Dutch

²“A Search Interface for my Questions”, IEEE 31(1999)2263-2270

³“My Personal Search-Engine”, IEEE 31(1999)2271-2279

Perl Foundation, the university's Computing Science Alumni group, and the CAC-ert certificate authority. He also has some long-term relation with the NLnet Foundation.